

D9.4: IP/Knowledge Management Plan

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Responsible Open Science in Europe

ROSiE

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Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	Austrian Agency for Research Integrity	OeAWi	Austria
3.	Partner	European Citizen Science Association	ECSA	Germany
4.	Partner	European Network of Research Ethics Committees	EUREC	Germany
5.	Partner	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	TSV	Finland
6.	Partner	High Council for the Evaluation of Research and Higher Education	Hceres	France
7.	Partner	National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment	INRAEe	France
8.	Partner	National Technical University of Athens	NTUA	Greece
9.	Partner	Universidade Católica Portuguesa	UCP	Portugal
10.	Partner	University of Latvia	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	University of Tartu	UT	Estonia
12.	Partner	University of Southeastern Norway	USN	Norway

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1 Introduction

The ROSiE project will produce knowledge which will be openly shared and all publications will be openly accessible. Knowledge in the form of research data generated in ROSiE will be made open access in data repositories in a suitably anonymised form. ROSiE does not utilise or rely on any foreground IP held and contributed by the partners.

2 Knowledge management plan

This section describes the knowledge management processes in relation to publications and textual deliverables (2.1), Training Materials (2.2), and Research data (2.3).

2.1 Publications and textual deliverables

Publications produced by the project and textual deliverables for the Commission will be produced on the basis of the research and development done in the ROSiE project. All textual deliverables are categorised as Public and will be made available on the project web-site when finally approved by the Commission. They will also be available on the Commission web-site. All publications will conform with the HORIZON 2020 open access requirements and will be published open access with an appropriate open access license. If possible in the relevant publication outlets a CC BY Creative Commons Attribution Licence will be chosen, or if the publication does not allow this the slightly more restrictive CC BY-NC license. All publications will also be deposited in relevant open access repositories.

2.2 Authorship

Authorship will be agreed and documented by the Work Package leader as early as possible during the development of a particular publication or deliverable. This agreement will specify who qualifies as authors, and the order of authors.

If the order of authors cannot be specified at an early stage, e.g. if the magnitude of contributions to the research is not yet fixed, the agreement will specify the process and criteria for determining the authorship order.

The criteria for qualification as an author will be the standard criteria within the biomedical field as specified by the International Council of Medical Journal Editors guidelines and by the practical interpretation of these guidelines..

2.3 Disagreement about authorship

As described in the preceding section the output development process involve reaching an authorship agreement at an early stage in the development of each output according to the standard authorship criteria within the biomedical field. If, however an authorship dispute later arises in relation to an output this will be mediated by the Project Coordinator (PC), or if the PC is involved in the publication or has another conflict of interest, by a Work Package Leader appointed by the Executive Board. The outcome of the mediation will be binding on all parties.

2.4 Training materials

ROSiE will develop a didactic framework and a range of training materials in Work Package 7. The online training materials will form part of the training e-platform created by the European Network of Research Ethics and Research Integrity (ENERI) and hosted by the European Commission platform SINAPSE. The training materials will also be made available on other appropriate open access platforms (e.g., the Embassy of Good Science) to accomplish deliverable 9.5. The materials will be distributed under an appropriate, non-restrictive open access license.

The authors of the didactic framework and of the different parts of the training materials will be clearly identified.

Contributors to video or audion content which is produced as part of the training materials will be identified in the materials and will assert their moral rights as performers, but not any financial performing rights.

2.5 Research data

ROSiE will generate research data from interviews, focus groups, and engagement events with a wide range of stakeholders and stakeholder groups. This data will be deposited in Zenodo or other appropriate open access data repositories, except in cases where qualitative data cannot be fully anonymised. We expect that the overwhelming majority of data can be fully anonymised. Research participants / stakeholders will be asked to provide explicit consent to deposition in a data repository as part of the informed consent process prior to data collection. The appropriate data repository for each dataset will be decided by the Executive Board, based on a recommendation from the Work Package leader of the relevant work package. All deposited data sets will be clearly identified as products of the ROSiE project and the support from the

Commission through HORIZON2020 explicitly stated. The persons who have contributed to the generation of the data set will be identified. All data sets will be quality assured before deposition (see D9.3 Quality Management Plan).

